

EFL Teachers' Pronunciation Cognition: Examining Practice Alignment and Comparative Cognitions of In-Service and Pre-Service Teachers

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Abstract: This study examines the cognition of pronunciation teaching among pre-service and in-service English teachers, investigating their beliefs about pronunciation instruction and the alignment between in-service teachers' cognitions and their classroom practices. Participants included 42 in-service secondary school English teachers and 51 pre-service teachers. Data were collected through an online survey and classroom observations. Quantitative survey data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and observational data were analyzed through frequency counts of pronunciation features, along with qualitative comparisons of teacher cognitions. Results revealed that pre-service and in-service teachers shared similar pronunciation teaching cognitions, with no significant differences attributed to demographic or professional factors. However, subtle intergroup variations emerged, and notable discrepancies were observed between in-service teachers' stated beliefs and actual practices. The findings underscore both the stability of core pronunciation teaching principles across professional stages and contextual adaptations that lead to cognition-practice misalignments. These results emphasize the need for reflective teacher training programs to bridge gaps between pedagogical orientations and classroom implementation.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Öğretmen sesletim bilişi

Sesletim öğretimi

İngilizce öğretmenleri

İngilizce öğretmen adayları

İngilizce Öğretmenlerin Sesletim Bilişi: İnançların Uygulamaya yansımaları

Özet: Bu çalışma, İngilizce öğretmen adayları ile İngilizce öğretmenlerinin sesletim öğretimine yönelik bilişlerini ve İngilizce öğretmenlerin bu bilişlerinin sınıf içi uygulamalara yansımaya düzeyini incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Araştırmaya, ilköğretim düzeyinde görev yapan 42 İngilizce öğretmeni ve 51 İngilizce öğretmen adayı katılmıştır. Veriler, sesletim öğretimi biliş ve stratejilerini değerlendiren bir anket ve İngilizce öğretmenlerinin ders gözlemleri yoluyla toplanmıştır. Nicel veriler tanımlayıcı istatistiklerle, gözlem verileri ise frekans analizleriyle incelenmiştir. Bulgular, öğretmen adayları ile İngilizce öğretmenlerinin sesletim öğretimine ilişkin benzer bilişlere sahip olduğunu ve demografik, mesleki faktörlerin anlamlı bir fark yaratmadığını göstermiştir. Gözlem sonuçları İngilizce öğretmenlerinin sesletim öğretimine yönelik bilişleri ile sınıf içi uygulamaları arasında farklar olduğunu göstermiştir. Sonuç olarak, pedagojik yönelimlerin sınıf içi uygulamalarla uyumlaştırılması için yansıtıcı öğretmen eğitiminin gerekliliği vurgulanmıştır.

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1. Introduction

Pronunciation is a critical component of oral English, yet it is often overlooked in language teaching (Foote & McDonough, 2017), foreign language teacher education (Burri et al., 2017), and language teaching (Huensch, 2019). A disconnect exists between advancements in pronunciation research and their implementation in classrooms, as highlighted by Euler (2014):

Even though by now, ELT experts and applied linguists have developed a sound foundation of language pedagogical methodology for the teaching of pronunciation and classroom materials for day-to-day teaching practice, many areas are still scarcely explored, and *most developments of the past 20 or so years do not seem to have found their way into teaching practice and teacher training* (Italics added) (p. 35).

In addition to the lack of correspondence between pronunciation research and classroom practices, there is a mismatch between teachers' beliefs and their classroom applications. Although teachers believe pronunciation should be taught communicatively and prioritize intelligibility over accent reduction, their practices often remain traditional, focusing on word-level features and repetitive drills (Buss, 2015). Most pronunciation instruction used in language classrooms over the years has remained essentially unchanged despite the 'four waves of instructional innovations' (Murphy & Baker, 2015). Factors such as English teachers, curricula, and classroom dynamics may have hindered the implementation of developments in pronunciation teaching over the past two decades. Three teacher-related issues—time, method, and focus—may prevent English teachers from addressing pronunciation in their lessons (Darcy, 2018).

As is widely acknowledged, although autonomous learners can learn English pronunciation by themselves to some extent, teachers have a profound impact on enhancing their students' pronunciation skills. The more importance teachers place on pronunciation, the more likely learners are to recognize its necessity for comprehensible communication. Teacher cognition—defined as beliefs, knowledge, and decision-making (Borg, 2003)—plays a key role in this disconnect. In underlining cognition and classroom practices, Baker (2011) underscores the connection between cognition and classroom practices, stating:

The classroom is a reflection of teachers' cognitions - their beliefs, their thoughts, their knowledge, their passions, their desires, their fears, and how these cognitions intersect with a variety of different contextual factors, limitations, and challenges that influence teachers' actions and behaviors (p. 203).

It is true to say that the mindset of teachers significantly impacts their attitudes in the classroom, determining what they choose to do or not do. In the realm of pronunciation instruction, English teachers' pronunciation cognition also holds significance. Foote et al. (2013) underline that pronunciation is heavily underemphasized in language teaching, receiving little attention compared to grammar and vocabulary, despite being studied in a highly communicative and intensive teaching context that seems ideal for teaching pronunciation as part of speaking skills.

Teacher cognition in language learning has been widely researched (Baker, 2011; Couper, 2019; Freeman et al., 2017; Georgiou, 2019), and pre-service teacher cognition has also been examined in language teaching (Buss, 2017; Trofimovich & Tsunemoto, 2023). However, no research has compared the pronunciation cognition of in-service and pre-service English teachers or examined how pre-service teachers' cognition relates to their actual classroom practices in Turkey. Consequently, this research aims to explore the cognition of in-service

English teachers regarding pronunciation teaching and its implementation in classrooms, and to compare the cognitions of in-service English teachers with those of pre-service English teachers. This study is significant in investigating the correspondence between in-service teachers' cognition of pronunciation teaching and its classroom implementation. Additionally, it aims to clarify why in-service teachers choose specific approaches to pronunciation teaching and what factors influence their choices. The study will also examine how teachers' cognition evolves and what circumstances influence this evolution. Ultimately, this research aims to bridge existing gaps in the field by prompting both pre-service and in-service teachers to reflect on their beliefs, attitudes, and strategies in pronunciation teaching, as well as the alignment between their practices and cognition.

1.1. Literature Review

The term pronunciation is commonly used in language learning and teaching to refer to how speech sounds are produced or articulated (Yates, 2014). However, pronunciation is not just about learning isolated sounds or mimicking an accent; it is about being understood and understanding others (Levis, 2022). It is shaped by a complex interaction of perceptual, articulatory, and interactional factors (Pennington & Richards, 1986).

Kelly (1969) metaphorically described pronunciation as the 'Cinderella' of language teaching, a description rooted in the neglect of pronunciation in language teaching, especially when compared to other language skills. Pronunciation teaching has a long history with many perspectives. The consensus in the 1980s that pronunciation instruction was ineffective, and that repetition was the only option (Derwing, 2010), under the influence of direct and audiolingual methods, changed with the emergence of communicative language teaching (CLT) (Brinton, 2017). Over the years, different approaches to pronunciation teaching have emerged, and distinct approaches have dominated each era. Among these, three approaches to teaching pronunciation —namely, the intuitive-imitative approach, the analytic-linguistic approach, and the integrative approach —emerge (Celce-Murcia et al., 1996).

Based on the premise that pronunciation learning occurs through exposure and practice rather than explicit instruction, the intuitive-imitative approach emphasizes learning pronunciation through listening to native speakers articulate, mimicking their pronunciation, and practicing until a certain degree of correctness and fluency is achieved. Conversely, the analytic-linguistic approach emphasizes explicit instruction, drawing on different tools such as the phonetic alphabet and articulatory descriptions, and focusing on the sounds and rhythm. The analytic-linguistic approach did not arise from the aim of replacing the former; rather, it emerged to complement the intuitive-imitative approach. The final approach, the integrative one, holds that pronunciation is an inseparable part of language learning. Since the goal is to communicate meaningfully, it has become vital to integrate pronunciation into other language skills, just as in real-life situations (Celce-Murcia et al., 1996).

Additionally, two approaches to specifying the content of pronunciation instruction, bottom-up and top-down, have dominated the field of pronunciation teaching. Top-down processing refers to a system of analyzing and comprehending language that depends primarily on the larger units of meaning (Evans, 1993). Instead of focusing on segmental units (vowels and consonants), it concentrates on suprasegmental units (e.g., stress, rhythm, intonation) of the language, emphasizing teaching pronunciation in the context of meaningful communication. The top-down approach contrasts with traditional methods by prioritizing broader aspects of communication, extending beyond the analysis of discrete sounds or their semantic significance, and aiming to encompass a comprehensive scope of linguistic phenomena

(Pennington, 1998). On the other hand, bottom-up is a form of inductive (data-driven) processing that starts with smaller and/or lower-ranked units and moves upward through larger and/or higher-ranked units (Moskovsky et al., 2015). It breaks down the language into individual units or components, such as word stress, syllables, and phonemes, in terms of pronunciation teaching.

1.1.1. Teacher cognition

The evolution of teaching has shifted focus from teacher behaviors to the significance of teacher cognition, where beliefs and knowledge serve as key determinants in understanding teaching practices and facilitating teacher development (Richardson, 2001). Teacher cognition encompasses the mental processes that occur within a teaching context, closely linked to the “hidden pedagogy of the classroom,” which includes beliefs, attitudes, expectations, and decisions that influence observable behaviors (Burns, 1992, p. 57). Öztürk (2021) presents teacher cognition in a tripartite model comprising teacher beliefs, knowledge, and thinking, which collectively form a holistic view of cognition. Teacher knowledge shapes decision-making and behaviors, informing educators on how best to foster effective learning environments (Carter, 1990, as cited in Verloop et al., 2001). Notably, the interactions among knowledge, beliefs, and contextual factors significantly influence teachers' planning, thinking, and decision-making processes, thereby guiding their interpretation of instructional strategies and outcomes (Charalambous, 2015).

The classroom setting plays a crucial role in teachers' professional development, where their perceptions are primarily shaped by experiences rather than formal teacher education programs (Denscombe, 1924). For instance, while teacher education programs emphasize detailed lesson planning for pre-service teachers, experienced teachers often find such practices impractical (Hall & Smith, 2006). Although educational theory lays the groundwork for real-life teaching, its implementation can be influenced by various factors, highlighting the divide between theory and practice (Burns, 1992). Clark and Peterson (1984) classified teachers' thought processes into planning, interactive thoughts, and theories and beliefs. Teacher planning encompasses thoughts before and after classroom interactions. The intertwining of teachers' understanding, actions, and various contextual elements, such as curriculum and student needs, evolves through their classroom experiences (Baker, 2014). Thus, teacher cognition can be defined as the “unobservable cognitive dimension of teaching—what teachers know, believe, and think” (Borg, 2003, p. 81).

1.1.2. Pre-service and in-service teacher cognition

Studies on teacher cognition include both in-service and pre-service teachers, as classroom experience is crucial in shaping their cognitive frameworks. Novice and experienced teachers represent different stages in teacher development, necessitating an understanding of their varying attitudes, beliefs, and knowledge (Sun & Zhang, 2022). Prior teaching experiences can enhance the connection between lesson content and instructional strategies, improving teachers' ability to adapt to different classroom situations (Sherin, 2002).

A study comparing knowledge-based reasoning among pre-service teachers, in-service teachers, and school principals found that the latter two utilized more knowledge-based reasoning (Gegenfurtner et al., 2020). Additionally, experienced teachers and principals displayed greater expertise in self-monitoring strategies. Differences in mental schemata were also noted, with novice teachers requiring classroom experience to develop suitable frameworks for interpreting classroom events, as indicated by Peterson and Comeaux's

(1987) examination of expert versus novice teachers. Practicum experiences are vital for pre-service teachers, as they provide their initial teaching exposure and significantly shape their cognition. Research has shown significant shifts in pre-service teachers' cognition related to learner-related challenges after their practicum (Çimen & Daloğlu, 2019). In contrast, Contreras et al. (2020) found that pre-service teachers exhibited more cognitive activity during lesson planning due to a focus on meticulous planning inherent in teacher education programs. A common factor influencing both groups is their prior language learning experiences, which play a pivotal role in their ongoing cognitive development (Sanchez, 2013).

1.1.3. Teacher cognition in language teaching

Language teacher cognition is distinct from cognition in other teaching areas due to the complexities of language instruction. Language teaching requires intricate mental processes informed by teachers' philosophies, beliefs, and personal experiences (Crooks, 2015). The dynamic nature of language teaching necessitates that teachers adapt their methods, influenced by their perceptions of second language acquisition (Woods, 1996) and the need for contextual negotiations to align pedagogical tools with teaching goals (Peng, 2024). Knowledge, beliefs, assumptions, and attitudes are crucial in shaping language teaching practices, which evolve throughout a teacher's career.

Beyond cognition, practical knowledge describes how teachers apply their expertise in real-time classroom situations. As sociocultural agents, teachers bring their beliefs, identities, and reasoning abilities into their practice, providing insights into their mental processes (Johnson, 2018). Context-based investigations of language teacher cognition have shown that classroom practices are influenced by teaching experience, training, and various language-related encounters within institutional contexts.

1.1.4. Teacher cognition of pronunciation teaching

Teaching pronunciation is challenging due to unclear guidelines and varying approaches (Darcy et al., 2012). Thus, teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and knowledge critically shape how they teach pronunciation features (Burns et al., 2015). Research indicates a consistent gap between teachers' stated beliefs and their classroom practices; for instance, Buss (2015) found that while EFL teachers hold positive views about pronunciation instruction, their practices primarily emphasize traditional methods, focusing on word-level features and repetition. Bai and Yuan (2019) also noted a significant mismatch between English teachers' cognitions and their actual practices, attributed to personal and contextual barriers, with low self-efficacy frequently cited as a primary obstacle.

Contextual factors often overshadow teachers' cognitive frameworks, resulting in discrepancies between their theoretical understanding of pronunciation instruction and its practical implementation. Baker (2014) asserts that curricular demands and student needs significantly reshape teachers' instructional approaches. Phipps and Borg (2009) argue that the tensions teachers face reflect competing influences on their cognition and behavior. Challenges such as anxiety about personal pronunciation proficiency, limited class time, assessment difficulties, and inadequate phonetic training intensify these discrepancies (Uchida & Sugimoto, 2018). Furthermore, teachers often lack training and rely on inadequate materials that overlook pronunciation (Couper, 2016, 2017). Exam-focused curricula may exacerbate these issues, as the pressure to cover prescribed content often sidelines pronunciation practice. Research highlights how insufficient pre-service training and limited

professional development can lead to uncertainty in effective teaching methods and materials, suggesting systemic gaps in support.

As noted earlier, there is a scarcity of research comparing the pronunciation teaching cognitions of pre- and in-service Turkish English teachers and the extent to which in-service English teachers' actual classroom practices of pronunciation teaching align with their cognitions. Therefore, this study will address the following research questions:

1. How do pronunciation teaching cognitions differ between pre-service and in-service teachers, considering factors such as experience, gender, pronunciation training background, teaching level, age, and teaching duration?
2. What are the pronunciation teaching techniques, features, and practices of in-service English teachers across different grade levels?
3. To what extent do the pronunciation teaching techniques, features, and practices of in-service English teachers align with their stated pronunciation teaching cognitions?

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

This study employed a quantitative design with two sequential phases to investigate the pronunciation cognitions of both pre-service and in-service English teachers. Additionally, it examined the extent to which in-service English teachers' cognitions about pronunciation teaching translate into their actual classroom practices—that is, how well these practices reflect their beliefs about pronunciation instruction. Structured observations of in-service English teachers focused on the pronunciation features covered during lessons, the frequency with which they were covered, and the methods and techniques used to teach those features. A week after the observations, a survey assessing the pronunciation cognitions of both pre-service and in-service English teachers was administered. Survey responses and observation frequencies will be compared using correlation analysis.

2.2. Participants

The data for this study were collected from 51 pre-service and 42 in-service English teachers working at state secondary schools in Antalya. Participants were selected using convenience sampling, a non-probability technique that involves recruiting individuals who are most accessible or willing to participate (Turner, 2020). This approach was chosen due to time constraints and the exploratory nature of the study. Participants' demographics (Table 1, Appendix A) provide a comprehensive overview of the demographic and professional characteristics of the 93 participants. The gender distribution shows a balanced representation, as both the pre-service (64.7% female, 35.3% male) and in-service (66.7% female, 33.3% male) groups have similar gender ratios, indicating no significant difference. In terms of age and experience, pre-service teachers predominantly fell within the younger range (64.7% aged 21–29, with only 4% over 30), while in-service teachers exhibited greater age diversity, with 33.3% aged 30–39 and 28.6% aged 40–49. Notably, pre-service teachers were novices, with no teaching experience beyond their practicum. Conversely, in-service teachers brought broader experience to their roles, with 31% having over 20 years of teaching experience.

A significant 76.3% of all participants were taught at the secondary school level. Furthermore, 45% of the teachers reported having a moderate accent without any communication issues, while only 1.1% indicated that their accents impeded communication.

A preference for American English was noted among pre-service teachers (37.3%), whereas in-service teachers more commonly favored British English (42.9%). Interestingly, 21.5% of all participants had no specific ideal accent model.

In terms of instructional time allocation, 35.5% reported dedicating 6–10 minutes for pronunciation instruction in each class, contrasted with only 6.5% who spent 15 minutes. Remarkably, just 38.7% had formal training, with no significant differences observed between groups. The most prevalent instructional practices included correcting mispronunciations (37.6%) and regularly incorporating pronunciation into lessons (22.6%). Only a minority of teachers (10.8%) utilized additional resources for pronunciation instruction.

2.3. Data Collection

Two data collection tools (i.e., observations and a survey) were utilized. The first data collection tool is structured observations carried out using a structured observation form. The form had three sections. The first section presents various pronunciation features in a table, including schwa, minimal pairs, and problematic sounds, allowing observers to tick the features covered by the teacher during lessons. The second section included a list of techniques used in pronunciation teaching. During the observations, the observers ticked the Yes box if the teacher covered a particular aspect of pronunciation. The last section included ten open-ended questions related to the lesson they observed. The survey developed by Tsunemoto and Trofimovich (2023) and Derwing et al. (2008) was conducted online using Google Forms. This survey consists of two sections. The first section was about demographic information. The second section included questions about the participants' pronunciation cognitions.

2.3.1. Observations

Ten in-service English teachers were each observed for four class hours over one week by two pre-service teachers (20 pre-service teachers total). In-service teachers at the same levels were observed during the same week while covering the same units. While the in-service teachers were informed about the general observation process, they were unaware of specific details (e.g., timing, duration, or focus). Observers used a structured observation form and underwent prior training, including a pilot observation of a two-hour video-recorded class. Inter-rater reliability (IRR) was excellent (Fleiss' $\kappa \geq 0.81$ for all codes during piloting; mean $\kappa = 0.83$ for 20% of reassessed observations).

2.3.2. Survey

An online survey was administered to 51 pre-service and 42 in-service English teachers. Pre-service teachers had already completed a 20-week mandatory practicum, ensuring their responses reflected their teaching experiences. Participants provided written consent after being informed of the study's purpose. The 20 pre-service teachers who conducted the observations were not given the survey to avoid bias.

2.4. Data Analysis

The analysis of the quantitative data from the survey was conducted using SPSS 22.0 software. The process began with analyses of missing values and outliers, followed by descriptive and comparative analyses. The choice of analytical technique was determined by the normality of the variables' distribution, assessed using four criteria.

First, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) and Shapiro-Wilk tests were employed, with the K-S test used for sample sizes larger than 35 and the Shapiro-Wilk test for smaller samples (McKillup, 2012). A significance value greater than 0.05 indicated a normal distribution. Second, a Z-test was used to assess the statistical significance of skewness and kurtosis. The p-value, calculated by dividing the skewness or kurtosis value by its standard error, was considered significant if less than 1.96 for $\alpha = 0.05$ or 2.58 for $\alpha = 0.01$ (Howitt & Cramer, 2011; Field, 2009; Hair et al., 1998). Third, skewness and kurtosis values between -1 and +1 were considered indicative of normal distribution (Büyüköztürk, 2016).

Variables meeting the majority of these criteria were deemed normally distributed and were analyzed using parametric techniques. For normally distributed variables with two sub-levels, independent samples t-tests were employed. For variables with three or more sub-levels, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used. Non-parametric techniques were applied to non-normally distributed data. Effect sizes were reported for statistically significant differences. For t-test results, Cohen's d was used (Small: 0.2; Medium: 0.5; Large: 0.8 and above). For ANOVA results, eta squared (η^2) was calculated (Small: 0.01; Medium: 0.06; Large: 0.14 and above) (Ulupınar & İnce, 2021).

The classroom observation data were analyzed by counting the frequency of pronunciation features covered in the lessons and comparing them with in-service English teachers' stated cognitions. To ensure reliability and validity, two researchers independently coded a subset (20%) of the data using a predefined codebook based on Celce-Murcia et al.'s (2010) framework (e.g., segmental errors, word stress). Inter-rater reliability was high (Cohen's $\kappa = .87$), with discrepancies resolved through discussion. Frequency counts of pronunciation features were triangulated with teacher survey data to assess congruence between stated cognitions and observed practices. To minimize bias, the two researchers were blinded to participants' survey responses during initial analysis. The coding protocol was refined through a pilot study (five observations), and member checking with six teachers confirmed interpretive accuracy. Transparent reporting of limitations (e.g., time constraints affecting instructional choices) further strengthens the study's validity.

3. Findings

The first research question examined the extent to which pronunciation teaching cognitions differ between pre-service and in-service teachers, considering factors such as experience, gender, pronunciation training background, teaching level, age, and teaching duration.

3.1. Pre-and In-Service Teachers' Pronunciation Teaching Cognitions

Both pre- and in-service English teachers share several common cognitions about pronunciation teaching, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Descriptive statistics of pronunciation teaching cognition

Themes	Pronunciation Teaching Beliefs Items	Pre-service		In-service		Overall	
		X*	SD	X*	SD	X*	SD
Importance of pronunciation	Pronunciation is one of the most important aspects of language for successful communication.	3.65	1.09	3.64	1.16	3.65	1.12
How pronunciation develops?	Pronunciation tends to develop naturally in English, even for learners who don't care about improving it.	3.47	0.92	3.52	1.09	3.49	1.00
	With effort, learners can modify their English pronunciation even if they've been pronouncing things a certain way for a long time.	3.92	0.87	3.86	1.00	3.89	0.93
	Learners' improvement in pronunciation has more to do with what they experience outside the classroom than it has to do with the instruction they receive.	3.63	0.96	3.69	1.02	3.66	0.98
	English pronunciation can be taught.	3.92	0.87	3.86	1.20	3.89	1.03
When to teach pronunciation?	In first- and second-year English language courses, pronunciation can be skipped to focus on other skills or areas of language.	2.47	1.16	2.57	1.23	2.52	1.19
	Teachers should target pronunciation early to prevent learners from reinforcing mistakes.	2.22	1.01	2.45	1.40	2.32	1.20
	Since pronunciation is a sensitive issue, teachers should only address it once students feel more confident in their ability to speak English.	3.47	1.06	3.24	1.12	3.37	1.09
What pronunciation features to teach?	Even if a class is made up of learners with different backgrounds, it's possible to identify a core set of English pronunciation features that students would benefit from focusing on.	3.59	0.92	3.67	0.95	3.62	0.93
	People who speak the same native language will face similar challenges in learning to pronounce a foreign language such as English.	3.78	1.15	3.50	1.31	3.66	1.23
	Learners' pronunciation issues that don't interfere with communication should be a lower priority for teachers to address.	3.25	1.06	3.14	1.12	3.20	1.08
How to teach pronunciation?	Teachers should develop objectives and activities for pronunciation like they do for other aspects of language.	3.98	0.95	3.86	1.14	3.92	1.03
	Pronunciation is something teachers should address on the spot in response to students' problems.	3.55	1.05	3.38	1.06	3.47	1.05
Who can teach pronunciation?	In helping learners to improve their pronunciation of English, it's more important to have training in teaching pronunciation than it is to have a native-like accent.	2.33	1.03	2.40	1.04	2.37	1.03
	It may not be politically correct, but I think anyone who teaches pronunciation should have a natively like accent.	2.90	1.35	2.98	1.02	2.94	1.21

Both groups share fundamental beliefs about pronunciation instruction, equally valuing its importance for communication and agreeing that pronunciation can be modified through effort, develops through both instruction and natural exposure, and should prioritize intelligibility over native-like accuracy. They also concurred with using structured objectives and generally support immediate error correction, though pre-service teachers show slightly stronger preference for this approach. However, key differences emerged in implementation: in-service teachers, drawing on classroom experience, favored early intervention to prevent mistakes and believed that pronunciation develops naturally, while pre-service teachers, likely

influenced by theoretical training, preferred delayed correction until students gained confidence and emphasized structured instruction. Additionally, pre-service teachers tended to assume uniform pronunciation challenges among learners sharing a native language, whereas in-service teachers recognized greater individual variability. These differences highlight how practical teaching experience leads to more nuanced, student-centered approaches while maintaining core principles about the importance and teachability.

The data in Table 3 (Appendix B) reveal a strong consensus between pre-service and in-service teachers on more pronunciation teaching principles, with both groups prioritizing intelligibility and rejecting notions that pronunciation instruction is boring or ineffective for beginners. While they share similar comfort levels teaching segmentals and prosody, and moderately endorse minimal pair drills, nuanced differences appeared in their approaches. Surprisingly, pre-service teachers showed a stronger attachment to traditional methods, such as minimal pairs, and greater skepticism about age barriers and the permanence of learning. In contrast, in-service teachers, shaped by classroom experience, showed greater confidence teaching beginners and a preference for communicative techniques, while exhibiting slightly stronger native-speaker bias. These differences appear to reflect how practical experience refines theoretical knowledge, although both groups shared foundational beliefs about communicative focus and intelligibility goals, suggesting that pronunciation teaching cognition evolves through professional practice without a radical transformation of core principles.

3.1.1. The relationship between pronunciation teaching cognition and experience

The statistical comparison presented in Table 4 (Appendix C) revealed no significant differences (all p -values > 0.05) between pre-service and in-service teachers regarding the significance of pronunciation, its development, when and what to teach, and who can teach it. Both categorized pronunciation as highly important for communication and supported a blend of instruction and natural exposure; they did not strongly favor rigid hierarchies, such as native-speaker dominance, nor did they advocate strict timing in pronunciation instruction. While both groups shared a preference for communicative, student-centered teaching strategies over rigid drills, subtle nuances exist. In-service teachers showed slightly more variability in their cognitions, suggesting their opinions may be shaped by classroom realities. They expressed more disagreement on whether pronunciation develops naturally or through explicit instruction and were more open to the concept of non-native speakers teaching pronunciation. In contrast, pre-service teachers tended to align closely with training program guidelines, favoring structured methods. The overall findings suggest that both teacher categories prioritized pronunciation similarly, albeit with some differences shaped by practical experience. This alignment suggests that while training effectively instills core principles, in-service experience refines these views based on the specific needs of individual learners.

3.1.2. Pronunciation teaching cognition and gender

No statistically significant gender differences were found in pronunciation teaching cognition ($p > 0.05$) across 5 out of 6 criteria, indicating strong alignment between male and female teachers in most areas. Both genders rated pronunciation as highly important for effective communication and agreed that pronunciation can be improved through a combination of instruction and exposure. Neither gender strongly advocated early or delayed instruction, and both favored communicative, student-centered techniques over rigid drills. Additionally, both minimally valued native-like accents and teaching skills are required. In short, gender did not significantly influence most pronunciation teaching cognitions, suggesting that both

genders share professional values, such as prioritizing intelligibility and rejecting native-speaker bias. However, male teachers tended to prioritize covering more features compared to female teachers.

3.1.3. Pronunciation teaching cognition and pronunciation training background

Analysis of the data revealed no significant gender differences in pronunciation teaching cognition, with no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) between teachers with pronunciation training (“Yes” group) and those without it (“No” group), indicating a strong alignment in their core cognitions about pronunciation teaching. Both groups considered pronunciation highly important for communication and critical to language learning. They acknowledged that a combination of instruction and natural exposure aids pronunciation development, and neither group strongly advocated for delaying pronunciation instruction nor prioritizing it early in the curriculum. While both groups focused on core features of pronunciation, trained teachers incorporated more nuanced aspects. They were inclined to favor communicative and student-centered techniques over rigid drills, and both groups minimally valued “nativelike” accents compared to teaching competence, emphasizing intelligibility over perfection and favoring practical methods such as communicative practice. This shared emphasis suggests that, whether trained or untrained, all participants agree on key principles of pronunciation teaching, implying that experience and intuition can compensate for a lack of formal training in shaping cognitions. While training refines perspectives, it does not significantly alter them, aligning with broader pedagogical trends.

3.1.4. Pronunciation teaching cognition and teaching levels

Despite differences in teaching levels, the data revealed broad agreement among educators on most pronunciation teaching cognitions. Teachers at all levels viewed pronunciation as important, with high school teachers rating its importance slightly higher; however, this difference is not statistically significant, indicating that pronunciation is universally valued regardless of student age. All groups agreed that pronunciation improves through both instruction and exposure. Teachers at the primary level targeted slightly more features, but all aligned with core intelligibility goals. Teachers across all levels likely favored communicative and adaptive techniques over rigid drills and minimally prioritized “nativelike” accents compared to teaching skills. High school teachers advocated for earlier instruction in pronunciation. In conclusion, teachers across primary, secondary, and high school shared core pronunciation teaching cognitions, differing primarily in timing—high school teachers start instruction earlier—and the scope of features, with primary teachers covering more.

3.1.5. Pronunciation teaching cognition and age ranges

The data in Table 5 (Appendix D) revealed no statistically significant differences across age groups (20–29 years, 30–39 years, 40–49 years) and pre-service teachers in all six pronunciation teaching criteria. This indicates strong alignment in their core cognitions, regardless of age or experience level. Both groups rated pronunciation as important and acknowledged that a combination of instruction and natural exposure aids in development. They favored focusing on intelligibility-driven features. Both groups preferred communicative and adaptive techniques over rigid drills and prioritized teaching skills over accent. Age and experience did not polarize cognition; pronunciation teaching principles are consistent across early-career, mid-career, and pre-service teachers. Both groups emphasized the importance of pronunciation, communicative methods, and inclusivity (accepting non-

native teachers). In conclusion, the findings showed that pronunciation teaching cognition is remarkably stable across age, with only minor, non-significant differences.

3.1.6. Pronunciation teaching cognition and teaching durations

The data in Table 6 (Appendix E) showed no statistically significant differences ($p > 0.05$) among all teaching experience groups (ranging from under 5 years to over 29 years) in terms of pronunciation teaching cognitions. This indicates a strong consensus among teachers, regardless of their years of experience. Teachers at all experience levels rated pronunciation as important and agreed that it improves through a mix of instruction and natural exposure. No experience group strongly advocated for either early or delayed teaching. All focused on core intelligibility features, with only minor variations, and favored communicative, adaptive techniques over rigid drills. They prioritized teaching skills over “nativelike” accents. In short, experience did not polarize cognition; teachers with 5 years or 30+ years of experience share nearly identical pronunciation teaching principles, emphasizing the importance of pronunciation for communication, flexible, student-centered methods, and inclusivity (accepting non-native teachers). In conclusion, teaching cognitions related to pronunciation are highly stable across teaching durations, suggesting that core pedagogical values are established early and persist throughout a teaching career.

3.2. Pronunciation teaching techniques, features, and practices of in-service English teachers

The second research question aimed to identify the pronunciation teaching techniques, features, and practices of in-service English teachers across different grade levels. Table 7 (Appendix F) presents the findings from observations on these techniques.

3.2.1. Pronunciation teaching techniques

The data in Table 7 (Appendix F) uncovered distinct patterns in technique usage across grades. Oral repetition, reading aloud, imitated pronunciation, and corrective feedback were the most frequently reported techniques in 5th and 6th grades (each appearing 5-7 times), but their use declined sharply in higher grades (2-3 instances in 7th-8th). Minimal pairs and communicative activities emerged only sporadically (0-4 instances in total), while more sophisticated methods, such as phonetic training (IPA) were entirely absent. Technology-based materials were used moderately in 5th grade (6 instances) but decreased in later grades (1-2 instances). Creative techniques (e.g., drama) and awareness-raising tasks were rarely employed (0-2 instances across all grades). Notably, 5th-grade teachers utilized the widest variety of techniques (11/12 listed), whereas 7th- and 8th-grade classrooms relied on a narrower repertoire (6-7 techniques), suggesting either curricular shifts or developmental appropriateness considerations in technique selection.

Five key patterns emerged from these findings: (1) lower grades relied predominantly on foundational techniques (repetition, imitation); (2) technique diversity diminished in higher grades; (3) phonetic training remained conspicuously absent at all levels; (4) communicative and creative methods were frequently underused; and (5) technology application varied significantly by grade, peaking in 5th grade before sharply declining. These trends collectively suggest either deliberate curricular prioritization or developmental assumptions about learners' evolving phonological needs. The consistent absence of certain research-supported methods (e.g., communicative practice) raises important questions about current pedagogical approaches to pronunciation instruction across secondary education levels.

3.2.2. *Pronunciation features*

Table 8 (Appendix G) revealed significant variations in how pronunciation features were addressed across grade levels. In 5th grade (7 instances), teachers most frequently covered problematic sounds (6 instances), schwa (5), and suprasegmental features like utterance stress (4) and intonation (3). Segmental features (consonant/vowel phonemes) also received moderate attention (4 instances each). However, 6th grade (5 instances) showed a shift toward word stress (3) and weak forms (3), with schwa and intonation maintaining consistent coverage (3 instances each). Notably, 7th- and 8th grades (2-3 instances) demonstrated markedly reduced focus, with only minimal pairs (2 in 7th), schwa (1 in 7th-8th), and accent varieties (2 in 8th) appearing sporadically. Striking absences included stress-timed rhythm (in one instance total) and connected speech (only in 5th grade), while construction stress appeared exclusively in 6th grade (in two instances). The data suggested a progressive decline in pronunciation feature coverage from lower to higher grades, with 5th-grade teachers addressing the broadest range of features (12 out of 14 listed) compared to 7th- and 8th-grade teachers (4-5 features). This pattern may reflect either curricular priorities or developmental assumptions about learners' phonological needs. Three salient patterns emerged from the data. First, a marked grade-level disparity was evident, with 5th-grade classrooms addressing two to three times as many pronunciation features as 7th-8th-grade classes. Second, instructional priorities shifted across grade levels: lower grades (5th-6th) consistently emphasized problematic segmentals (e.g., /θ/), schwa, and suprasegmental features, such as utterance stress, whereas higher grades (7th-8th) focused sparingly on minimal pairs and accent varieties. Third, systemic gaps were observed across all grades, with connected speech, stress-timed rhythm, and construction stress receiving negligible attention despite the consistent coverage of schwa and intonation. This progressive decline in feature coverage suggests either diminishing curricular priority or tacit assumptions about older learners' reduced need for phonological support.

3.2.3. *Pronunciation practices*

The data revealed several commonalities in how in-service teachers approach pronunciation instruction, despite variations in grade levels (5th-8th) and teaching contexts. Most teachers (e.g., T1, T4, T5, T6, T7, T8, T9, T10) employed explicit methods, such as direct correction and repetition. A few teachers (T2, T3, T10 in the second grade) utilized implicit techniques, such as modeling in context. Immediate correction was a common practice among most teachers (T4, T5, T6, T7, T8, T9, T10), while only T10 (first grade) showed no response to errors.

The findings indicated a limited allocation of time for pronunciation instruction, as most teachers dedicated little to no time to pronunciation. Only T6 (1-2 minutes) and T8 (5-10 minutes) provided explicit time for pronunciation, while others (e.g., T1, T2, T3, T4, T7, T9, T10) integrated it incidentally or skipped it entirely. Most teachers preferred to focus on individual sounds rather than prosody (suprasegmentals), targeting specific phonemes (e.g., T1, T4, T6, T9). Only two teachers (T2 and T10) integrated pronunciation with listening and reading activities, but they still lacked a focus on prosody.

Moreover, the majority of teachers (T1, T3, T4, T5, T7, T8, T9, T10) adopted inflexible teaching approaches, adhering to rigid correction routines, such as repeating words or sentences. In contrast, T2, T6, and T8 (in the second session) demonstrated flexibility by incorporating interactive tasks. The results also showed limited support for student confidence, with only T2, T6, and T10 (second grade) associating pronunciation with high

confidence. There was also poor integration of pronunciation with other skills, as few teachers link it to speaking (T4, T9), listening/reading (T2, T10), or grammar (T8). Many teachers neglected pronunciation entirely or addressed it minimally (e.g., T6: 1–2 minutes, T8: 5–10 minutes).

In conclusion, while in-service teachers tended to adopt a reactive approach to pronunciation—correcting errors explicitly—they generally lacked proactive instruction, such as dedicated time and prosody work, as well as student-centered practices, like boosting confidence and integrating skills. Teachers prioritized correcting errors but rarely taught pronunciation systematically, focusing more on segmental features than suprasegmental aspects. The findings suggest that pronunciation teaching is often incidental or rushed, and that many teachers miss opportunities to build student confidence, opting for rigid correction methods over adaptive, communicative strategies.

3.3. Alignment and discrepancies between in-service English teachers' pronunciation teaching cognitions (survey data) and practices (observation data)

Our third research question probed the extent to which the pronunciation teaching techniques, features, and practices of in-service English teachers align with their pronunciation teaching cognitions. The results revealed both alignments and contradictions between teachers' stated cognitions about pronunciation instruction and their actual classroom practices. Teachers consistently emphasized intelligibility over native-like accuracy in their survey responses, a principle reflected in their observed focus on problematic sounds and core segmentals rather than accent perfection. Both datasets also confirmed teachers' preference for immediate error correction and minimal time allocation to pronunciation, with only 6.5% dedicating 15 minutes or more per class, and most lessons showing either incidental treatment (1-2 minutes) or complete omission. However, significant discrepancies emerged between teachers' communicative ideals and their traditional practices. While survey responses strongly endorsed student-centered, adaptive techniques, as Ismayilli et al. (2025) suggest, classroom observations revealed an overwhelming reliance on rigid drills, such as oral repetition (5-7 instances in lower grades), and corrective feedback, with a near-total absence of research-backed methods, including IPA training or stress-timed rhythm practice. Similarly, although teachers reported feeling comfortable teaching suprasegmental features, observations revealed disproportionate attention to segmentals, with only two teachers incorporating prosodic elements. This theory-practice gap extends to confidence-building and skill integration. While teachers valued these concepts theoretically, few implemented them, with only three teachers linking pronunciation to learner confidence and sporadic integration with other skills observed. Underlying these contradictions are systemic issues: a pronounced curricular decline in pronunciation focus across grade levels (from 12 features addressed in 5th grade to just 4 in 8th grade) despite no survey support for delayed instruction, and inadequate training (reported by just 38.7% of teachers) that fails to translate cognitions into effective practices. The findings suggest that teachers' research-aligned philosophies are constrained by practical factors, including time limitations, resource gaps, and entrenched instructional habits. This highlights the need for targeted professional development that bridges cognitive principles with classroom implementation through modeling of communicative techniques, suprasegmental training, and time-management strategies.

4. Discussion

This study explored the cognitions of pre- and in-service English teachers regarding pronunciation teaching and examined how the cognitions of in-service teachers regarding

pronunciation teaching align with their classroom practices. The findings reveal stability and variation in these cognitions, influenced by factors such as experience, gender, pronunciation training background, teaching level, age, and teaching duration. Notably, both pre- and in-service teachers demonstrated a strong consensus on foundational principles, emphasizing the importance of pronunciation for communication and prioritizing intelligibility over native-like accuracy. They agreed on the teachability of pronunciation and rejected deterministic views such as age barriers or fossilization, favoring communicative strategies over rigid drills.

Despite their shared views on core principles, nuanced perspectives emerged, likely driven by experience. In-service teachers, influenced by classroom realities, favored early intervention to prevent fossilization and acknowledged individual variability in learner challenges. Observations of in-service teachers revealed a reliance on traditional methods and techniques, such as repetition and corrective feedback, indicating a discrepancy between stated beliefs and actual practices. Reliance on outdated techniques aligns well with previous studies (Hismanoglu & Hismanoglu, 2011; Szyszka, 2016; Tergujeff, 2012). In contrast, pre-service teachers, influenced by their recent theoretical training, leaned toward delayed correction and assumed uniform L1-based difficulties. This divergence appears to underscore how practical experience refines theoretical knowledge, with both groups retaining foundational beliefs about communicative focus and intelligibility goals, indicating that pronunciation teaching cognition evolves through professional practice without a radical transformation of core principles.

Interestingly, factors such as gender, age, teaching level, and years of experience had a minimal impact on cognitions, suggesting a significant role for robust professional socialization. Previous research on the influence of experience showed conflicting findings. For example, in synch with our findings, Kanoksilapatham (2014) found that the age of English teachers had an insignificant effect on their competence in teaching pronunciation. However, Georgiou (2018) revealed that age was critical for the teachers' cognitions since the oldest age group reported different cognitions regarding teaching pronunciation. Moreover, the lack of substantial influence from a pronunciation training background, which supports Yağız's (2018) finding, implies that experiential knowledge may compensate for formal training, leading to a shared emphasis on key principles. While training refines perspectives, it does not appear to alter them fundamentally, aligning with broader pedagogical trends. Thus, pronunciation teaching cognitions regarding teaching duration appear stable across all experience levels, indicating that core pedagogical values are established early in a teacher's career.

Another key finding relates to how various factors shape the pronunciation teaching practices of in-service teachers. Grade-level differences were observed in their practices, where they emphasized traditional techniques (e.g., repetition and imitation) in lower grades (5th–6th) and focused more on minimal pairs in higher grades (7th–8th). This shift may stem from perceived learner autonomy or curricular changes at higher levels. However, the consistent absence of research-backed methods, particularly connected speech, raises critical concerns about the pedagogical approaches to pronunciation instruction across secondary education levels. The gradual decline in feature coverage suggests diminishing curricular priority or tacit assumptions about older learners' reduced need for phonological support.

Our investigation of the alignment between in-service teachers' cognitions and their classroom practices revealed that contradictions outweighed alignments. While teachers emphasized intelligibility and avoided accent perfection in their cognitions, classroom

observations showed a predominant focus on oral repetition and corrective feedback. This prominent reliance on rigid drills, despite a theoretical endorsement of student-centered techniques, highlights a significant theory-practice gap. Such discrepancies resonate with Borg's (2003) model of teacher cognition, wherein contextual factors—including time pressures and curricular demands—can overshadow research-based beliefs.

Furthermore, while teachers reported comfort with suprasegmentals, classroom observations indicated a disproportionate focus on segmental features (e.g., consonant/vowel phonemes), with only two teachers incorporating prosodic elements. This mirrors findings from Derwing and Munro (2005), who noted a prioritization of segmentals over suprasegmentals, suggesting a pervasive trend despite evidence supporting the latter's role in enhancing intelligibility. Another surprising mismatch was the allocation of time: despite teachers' cognitions emphasizing the importance of pronunciation, actual classroom practices allocated minimal time—often fewer than five minutes per lesson—to this important aspect of language learning. As instructional focus shifted dramatically from 12 features in 5th grade to just four in 8th grade, it raises questions about curricular assumptions regarding older learners. These findings align with prior research on theory-practice gaps in pronunciation instruction. For instance, Buss (2015) observed that despite EFL teachers' positive cognitions, their practices prioritized traditional, word-level drills—a pattern mirrored in our study. Similarly, Bai and Yuan (2019) identified contextual barriers (e.g., low self-efficacy, curricular pressures) as key drivers of such discrepancies, while Baker (2014) noted how institutional demands reshape instructional choices. These tensions reflect broader conflicts between cognition and behavior, as Phipps and Borg (2009) theorized. Compounding these issues are systemic challenges, such as anxiety about pronunciation proficiency, time constraints, and inadequate training (Couper, 2016, 2017; Uchida & Sugimoto, 2018). These challenges, exacerbated by exam-driven curricula that often marginalize pronunciation, further illuminate the need for targeted professional development. Such initiatives should bridge cognitive principles with classroom implementation by modeling communicative techniques, providing suprasegmental training, and effective time-management strategies.

In conclusion, while our findings highlight the stability of core pedagogical values across experience levels, they also underscore the need for greater coherence between teachers' beliefs and their instructional practices. Addressing the theory-practice gap is essential to fostering more effective pronunciation instruction that aligns with the evolving understanding of language teaching.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the resilience of core pronunciation teaching cognitions between pre- and in-service English teachers and across in-service English teacher demographics and experience levels, underscoring the effectiveness of teacher education in establishing shared principles. However, the persistent theory-practice gap in in-service English teachers' cognitions and actual classroom practices, already demonstrated (e.g., Bai & Yuan, 2019; Buss, 2015), despite the 'four waves of instructional innovations' (Murphy & Baker, 2015)—driven mainly through curricular, training, and contextual factors—calls for pragmatic interventions. The reasons why developments of the past 20 or so years in pronunciation teaching have not found their way into teaching practice and teacher training" (Euler, 2014, p. 35) are also worth exploring. Pre-service English teachers' cognitions about pronunciation teaching, which share many similarities with those of experienced in-service teachers,

particularly in their prioritization of old-fashioned pronunciation teaching techniques, also require scrutiny of the current language teaching method-related courses.

While the current study provides valuable insights into the cognition and practices of pre-service and in-service English teachers regarding pronunciation teaching, its generalizability is limited by the sample size (42 in-service and 51 pre-service teachers) and limited observations (10 teachers over four class hours). The uneven grade-level distribution (5th–8th) and short observation window may obscure nuanced practices. Future research could employ longitudinal designs to track the dynamics of cognition and practice as teachers transition from training to the profession. Additionally, exploring institutional barriers (e.g., how standardized tests marginalize pronunciation) may deepen understanding of systemic disinterest.

To address the theory-practice gap, we propose a multifaceted approach beginning with curriculum redesign, where grade-level guidelines should integrate explicit pronunciation modules into textbooks, ensuring a balance between segmental and suprasegmental features. Structured rubrics (e.g., Bloom's taxonomy) could improve formative/summative evaluation of pronunciation (Budiharso et al., 2024). Teacher training must also be enhanced through workshops that model communicative techniques, such as task-based minimal pair activities, while providing strategies for effective time management—for instance, embedding suprasegmental practice into existing speaking tasks to minimize perceived workload. Additionally, technology, particularly AI tools, could play a key role in supplementing teacher feedback and bridging self-efficacy gaps among learners. Furthermore, AI/chatbots are innovative solutions for pronunciation practice (e.g., reducing anxiety, providing feedback) (Çakmak, 2022). Further research is needed, including longitudinal studies and replications to strengthen generalizability, as well as investigations into technology-assisted pronunciation instruction to uncover new pathways for alignment. Ultimately, closing this gap demands systemic collaboration among policymakers, teacher educators, and practitioners to prioritize pronunciation as a fundamental communicative skill rather than an afterthought.

Ethical Issues

The study received ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of Akdeniz University (No: 861091, 22.02.2024). This study is based on the second author's master's thesis.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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Appendices

Appendix A. Participants' demographic statistics

Variable	Sub-category	Pre-service Teachers		Inservice Teachers		Total		Difference*
		N	%	N	%	N	%	X^2/p
Gender	Male	18	35.3	14	33.3	32	34.4	$X^2=0.039$ $p=0.743$
	Female	33	64.7	28	66.7	61	65.6	
Age	Under 20	1	2.0	3	7.1	4	4.3	$X^2=53.923$ $p<0.001$
	21-29	33	64.7	9	21.4	42	45.2	
	30-39	1	2.0	14	33.3	15	16.1	
	40-49	1	2.0	12	28.6	13	14.0	
	50-59	-	-	4	9.5	4	4.3	
	Pre-service teacher	15	29.4	-	-	15	16.1	
Teaching Level	Primary school	5	9.8	8	19.0	13	14.0	$X^2=5.539$ $p=0.136$
	Secondary school	42	82.4	29	69.0	71	76.3	
	High school	2	3.9	5	11.9	7	7.5	
	None	2	3.9	-	-	2	2.2	
Teaching Duration	Under 5 years	46	90.2	11	26.2	57	61.3	$X^2=41.408$ $p<0.001$
	6-9 years	2	3.9	4	9.5	6	6.5	
	10-14 years	1	2.0	5	11.9	6	6.5	
	15-19 years	-	-	9	21.4	9	9.7	
	More than 20 years	2	3.9	13	31.0	15	16.1	
Accent Profile	Native-like and can communicate easily	6	11.8	8	19.0	14	15.1	$X^2=2.015$ $p=0.733$
	Slightly accented but can communicate easily	18	35.3	12	28.6	30	32.3	
	Moderately accented but no communication problems	23	45.1	19	45.2	42	45.2	
	Heavily accented but does not impede communication	3	5.9	3	7.1	6	6.5	
	Heavily accented and impede communication	1	2.0	-	-	1	1.1	
Pronunciation Model	American English	19	37.3	8	19.0	27	29.0	$X^2=16.382$ $p=0.037$
	British English	8	15.7	18	42.9	26	28.0	
	No ideal English pronunciation model	11	21.6	9	21.4	20	21.5	
	American and British	10	19.6	4	9.5	14	15.1	
	American-British and Other	1	2.0	-	-	1	1.1	
	American-No ideal	2	3.9	-	-	2	2.2	
	British-No ideal	-	-	1	2.4	1	1.1	
	American-British-No ideal	-	-	1	2.4	1	1.1	
International English	-	-	1	2.4	1	1.1		
Time Spent for Teaching Pronunciation in a Class Hour	More than a minute	5	9.8	1	2.4	6	6.5	$X^2=5.507$ $p=0.481$
	Less than 5 minutes	17	33.3	9	21.4	26	28.0	
	6-10 minutes	15	29.4	18	42.9	33	35.5	
	11-15 minutes	8	15.7	9	21.4	17	18.3	
	16-20 minutes	3	5.9	2	4.8	5	5.4	
	21-25 minutes	1	2.0	2	4.8	3	3.2	
Pronunciation Training/Course Background	Yes	22	43.1	14	33.3	36	38.7	$X^2=0.933$ $p=0.334$
	No	29	56.9	28	66.7	57	61.3	
Pronunciation Practice	I try to incorporate pronunciation regularly (1)	12	23.5	9	21.4	21	22.6	$X^2=5.412$ $p=0.492$
	I regularly correct mispronounced words (2)	21	41.2	14	33.3	35	37.6	
	I incorporate other resources to teach pronunciation in my regular EFL classroom (3)	3	5.9	7	16.7	10	10.8	
	All that applies	8	15.7	5	11.9	13	14.0	
	Both 1 and 2	4	7.8	5	11.9	9	9.7	
	Both 2 and 3	3	5.9	1	2.4	4	4.3	
Both 1 and 3	-	-	1	2.4	1	1.1		

Appendix B. Descriptive Statistics of Pronunciation Teaching Beliefs

Pronunciation Teaching Beliefs (2) Items	Pre-service		Inservice		Overall	
	X*	SD	X*	SD	X*	SD
Teaching pronunciation does not usually result in permanent changes.	2.71	1.06	2.50	0.99	2.61	1.03
Drilling minimal pairs is the best way to teach pronunciation.	3.45	0.86	3.26	0.73	3.37	0.80
Communicative practice is the best way to teach pronunciation.	4.06	0.90	4.10	0.98	4.08	0.94
Teaching pronunciation is boring.	2.41	0.98	2.10	0.79	2.27	0.91
Pronunciation teaching should help make students comfortably intelligible to their listeners.	3.96	0.89	3.83	1.03	3.90	0.96
You can't teach pronunciation to lower levels.	2.14	0.98	2.02	0.95	2.09	0.96
Only native speakers should teach pronunciation.	2.16	1.12	2.24	1.05	2.19	1.09
There is an age-related limitation on the acquisition of native-like pronunciation.	2.90	1.17	2.79	1.12	2.85	1.14
Pronunciation instruction is only effective for highly motivated learners.	2.71	1.08	2.98	1.20	2.83	1.14
I'm completely comfortable teaching segmentals.	3.24	0.81	3.36	0.88	3.29	0.84
I'm completely comfortable teaching all aspects of prosody (suprasegmentals).	3.20	0.87	3.14	0.95	3.17	0.90

Appendix C. Comparison Results of Pronunciation Beliefs by Teacher Category

Criteria	Group	N	X̄	SD	t	p
Importance of pronunciation	Pre-service	51	3.65	1.09	0.02	0.986
	Inservice	42	3.64	1.16		
How pronunciation develops	Pre-service	51	14.94	2.80	0.02	0.985
	Inservice	42	14.93	3.53		
When to teach pronunciation	Pre-service	51	8.16	2.05	-0.22	0.826
	Inservice	42	8.26	2.55		
What pronunciation features to teach	Pre-service	51	10.63	2.27	0.62	0.540
	Inservice	42	10.31	2.72		
How to teach pronunciation	Pre-service	51	7.53	1.80	0.75	0.458
	Inservice	42	7.24	1.96		
Who can teach pronunciation	Pre-service	51	5.24	1.53	-0.49	0.623
	Inservice	42	5.38	1.27		

Appendix D. Comparison Results of Pronunciation Beliefs by Age Range

Criteria	Group	N	X̄	SD	F	p
Importance of pronunciation	20-29	42	3.69	1.16	0.06	0.979
	30-39	15	3.60	1.18		
	40-49	13	3.77	1.17		
	Pre-service	15	3.73	0.70		
How pronunciation develops	20-29	42	14.76	3.43	0.83	0.481
	30-39	15	14.73	3.31		
	40-49	13	16.00	1.78		
	Pre-service	15	15.67	1.84		
When to teach pronunciation	20-29	42	8.55	2.07	0.74	0.532
	30-39	15	8.07	2.89		
	40-49	13	7.69	2.84		
	Pre-service	15	7.73	1.83		
What pronunciation features to teach	20-29	42	10.74	2.58	0.34	0.795
	30-39	15	10.07	2.87		
	40-49	13	10.31	1.80		
	Pre-service	15	10.73	2.22		
How to teach pronunciation	20-29	42	7.40	2.02	0.76	0.523
	30-39	15	6.80	2.08		
	40-49	13	7.69	1.55		
	Pre-service	15	7.67	0.98		
Who can teach pronunciation	20-29	42	5.31	1.49	0.31	0.818
	30-39	15	4.93	1.62		
	40-49	13	5.31	1.44		

	Pre-service	15	5.40	1.30
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*One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Appendix E. Comparison Results of Pronunciation Beliefs by Teaching Duration

Criteria	Group	N	X̄	SD	F	p
Importance of pronunciation	Under 5 years	57	3.72	1.05	1.12	0.355
	6-9 years	6	3.00	1.26		
	10-14 years	6	4.00	1.26		
	15-19 years	9	3.89	0.93		
	More than 29 years	15	3.33	1.35		
How pronunciation develops	Under 5 years	57	14.91	3.25	0.53	0.718
	6-9 years	6	14.83	1.72		
	10-14 years	6	16.67	1.63		
	15-19 years	9	14.56	3.17		
	More than 29 years	15	14.60	3.60		
When to teach pronunciation	Under 5 years	57	8.07	2.09	0.97	0.429
	6-9 years	6	9.33	1.37		
	10-14 years	6	9.33	3.78		
	15-19 years	9	7.56	2.24		
	More than 29 years	15	8.20	2.54		
What pronunciation features to teach	Under 5 years	57	10.44	2.65	0.92	0.454
	6-9 years	6	11.67	1.75		
	10-14 years	6	11.67	2.50		
	15-19 years	9	10.11	1.54		
	More than 29 years	15	9.93	2.43		
How to teach pronunciation	Under 5 years	57	7.32	1.96	0.22	0.929
	6-9 years	6	7.17	1.72		
	10-14 years	6	7.83	1.47		
	15-19 years	9	7.78	1.56		
	More than 29 years	15	7.40	2.06		
Who can teach pronunciation	Under 5 years	57	5.28	1.50	0.26	0.902
	6-9 years	6	5.33	1.51		
	10-14 years	6	4.83	1.60		
	15-19 years	9	5.33	1.41		
	More than 29 years	15	5.53	1.06		

*One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Appendix F. Distribution of Pronunciation Teaching Techniques Across Grade Levels

Pronunciation Teaching Techniques	Distribution of Pronunciation Teaching Techniques Across Grade Levels			
	5th grade (7)	6th grade (5)	7th grade (2)	8th grade (3)
Oral repetition	7	5	1	2
Reading aloud	7	5	2	2
Imitated pronunciation	7	4	0	1
Minimal pairs (e.g., ship and sheep / white and light)	0	0	2	0
Phonetic training (IPA)	0	0	0	0
Awareness-raising tasks	1	1	0	0
Creative techniques (drama, etc.)	2	0	0	1
Ear training	1	3	0	0
Corrective feedback	7	5	2	3
Technology-based materials	6	2	1	2
Integration with other skills	1	3	1	1
Communicative activities	3	4	2	0

Appendix G. Pronunciation Features Covered

Pronunciation Features Covered	Number of Instances Pronunciation Features Covered Across Grades			
	5 th Gr.	6 th Gr.	7 th Gr.	8 th Gr.
	(7)	(5)	(2)	(3)
Problematic sounds (e.g., the <i>th</i> sounds [thanks, mother])	6	0	0	2
Schwa /ə/	5	3	1	1
Minimal pairs (e.g., <i>ship</i> and <i>sheep</i>)	3	0	2	1
Word stress (e.g., guitar = guiTAR)	2	3	2	0
Weak forms (e.g., I need an answer = “I” and “an” are less strong than other words)	3	3	0	0
Utterance stress (e.g., I want that BAG or I want THAT bag)	4	3	0	0
Stress-timed rhythm (e.g., COWS EAT GRASS takes roughly the same time to say as the COWS could EAT the GRASS)	0	1	1	0
Intonation (e.g., We have homework tonight [falling] and We have homework tonight [rising])	3	3	1	1
Connected speech (e.g. <i>Send it</i> sounds like <i>sen.dit</i> ; <i>short time</i> sounds like <i>shortime</i>)	3	0	0	0
Accent varieties (e.g. British English vs. American English).	0	1	0	2
The process of thought grouping (a group of words that belong together)	3	1	0	0
Prominence (sentence-level stress)	2	2	0	0
Construction stress (e.g. how affixation impacts word stress)	0	2	0	0
Consonant phonemes (the basic inventory)	4	1	0	0
Vowel phonemes (the basic inventory)	4	2	0	0

Number of instances pronunciation features covered across grades